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Hate Speech and Campus Disunity Among Undergraduates Students of Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi: A Search for Positive Values and Social Co-Existence

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ABSTRACT

Hate speech among undergraduate students has emerged as a significant factor undermining social cohesion and academic engagement in Nigerian universities. This study investigates the prevalence of hate speech, its contribution to campus disunity, the social and academic implications, and the role of positive values in promoting student unity at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. The study is anchored in Émile Durkheim's Social Solidarity and Social Value Theory which posits that shared moral values and collective conscience are essential for social cohesion. Employing a mixed-methods research design, data were collected from 400 undergraduate students across all levels using structured questionnaires and semi-structured interview. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages), while qualitative data were thematically analyzed. The findings reveal that hate speech is prevalent among students and significantly contributes to mistrust, segregation along ethnic and religious lines, reduced intergroup interactions, conflicts, and diminished trust in institutional authorities. It further adversely affects student social relations, collaborative learning, campus participation, and psychological wellbeing. Conversely, positive values such as tolerance, empathy, respect, dialogue, and mentorship were identified as critical in promoting unity, and fostering peaceful coexistence. The study recommends the integration of value-based education, structured mentorship programs, and awareness campaigns to strengthen social cohesion on campus. The findings have practical implications for university administrators, student leaders, and policymakers, providing evidence-based strategies to address hate speech and promote positive student interactions. A limitation of the study is its focus on a single university, which may affect generalizability to other contexts. Nevertheless, it offers valuable insights for designing preventive and corrective strategies for fostering unity among undergraduates.

Keywords: Hate speech, Campus disunity, Positive values, Social coexistence, Undergraduate students, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Universities are not just centres for academic instruction; they are also laboratories for nation-building. They bring together young and old people from diverse ethnic, religious, and cultural backgrounds and prepare them for leadership roles in society. Ideally, the university environment aside being a citadel of knowledge promoting scholarship should equally promote dialogue, mutual respect, and critical thinking

for solving societal problems. Unfortunately, the growing prevalence of hate speech on campuses threatens these ideals.

Hate speech and hate crimes have become a pervasive issue globally, affecting various communities. The widespread nature of this problem is evident in the increasing number of incidents reported worldwide. According to FBI's hate crimes Statistics report, there were 11,679 hate crimes involving 13,243 victims in United State alone in 2020 (FBI,2020). The incidents were motivated by bias against various groups, including racial, ethnic, and religious minorities as well as individuals with disabilities among others. In Africa, Rwanda has a good example of country that has witnessed the disaster and horror of hate speech and crimes. In Nigeria, hate speech has been a significant concern, particularly in the context of ethnic and religious tensions. The country has witnessed various incidents of hate speech and violence, often fueled by misinformation and extremist ideologies (Adeyemi, 2018, Ben-David & Mattsson, 2019). More disturbing, with the rise of social media has enabled the spread of hateful speech in the social and political space which contribute to offline violence and hate crimes making the issue of hate speech and hate crimes a worrisome social problem deserving urgent and collective attention especially as Nigeria prepares for 2027 general elections. Hate speech therefore, has emerged as a critical challenge particularly with the advent of social media platforms, a trend in vogue even among students on campuses. In Nigeria, where identity-based tensions already define national politics, campuses increasingly reproduce the same divisions that plague the wider society (Babatunde, 2023). This paper therefore interrogates how hate speech manifests within university spaces, how it fuels Hate speech has been widely defined as expressions that demean, stigmatize, or incite hostility against individuals or groups based on identity markers such as ethnicity, religion, or political affiliation (Waldron, 2012). Within campus environments, such expressions undermine mutual trust, weaken social bonds, and erode the collective identity necessary for peaceful coexistence. At Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, the student population is ethnically and religiously diverse. This article therefore examines hate speech as a contributory factor to campus disunity among undergraduate students of Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, while exploring the role of positive values in fostering social coexistence.

2. Statement of the Problem

Hate speech has become a persistent social problem in Nigeria, reflecting deep-seated ethnic, religious, and political divisions. While national attention has focused largely on hate speech in political discourse and social media, its presence within university campuses has received limited scholarly attention. At Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, undergraduate students come from diverse ethnic, religious, and socio-political backgrounds. Ideally, such diversity should promote intercultural learning and unity. However, anecdotal observations and student experiences suggest increasing cases of verbal hostility, stereotyping, exclusionary narratives, and online hate expressions among students. The persistence of hate speech on campus has contributed to: Social segregation among students, weakening of intergroup trust, declining sense of collective student identity and increased tension during student political activities.

Despite these realities, institutional responses have largely focused on disciplinary control rather than addressing the underlying value deficits that sustain hate speech. Moreover, there is limited empirical and conceptual work examining how hate speech affects campus unity and social coexistence in Nigerian universities, particularly within state-owned institutions. Existing literature on hate speech in Nigeria has largely focused on political communication, electoral violence, and online media (Akinola & Adesina, 2020; Waldron, 2012, Babatunde, 2023). While these studies provide important insights, they reveal several gaps: specifically failed to addresses hate speech within university campuses, and also considering undergraduate students are under-represented in empirical discussions on hate speech and hate crimes. Also, many studies emphasize regulation and punishment, with little attention to positive values and social coexistence as preventive mechanisms. This study fills these gaps by situating hate speech within a campus environment and emphasizing values-driven approaches to unity. This study therefore addresses the problem of insufficient understanding of hate speech as a driver of campus disunity and the neglect of value-based solutions to promote peaceful coexistence. The major questions that this study answers are:

1. What forms of hate speech are prevalent among undergraduate students of Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi?
2. How does hate speech contribute to campus disunity among undergraduate students?
3. What are the perceived consequences of hate speech on social relations and student interactions on campus?
4. What positive values can promote social coexistence and unity among students?

Hypothesis

There is a significant relationship between hate speech and campus disunity

Review of Relevant Literature

Conceptualizing Hate Speech in Campus Contexts

Hate speech goes beyond offensive language; it represents a social mechanism through which power, exclusion, and dominance are reproduced (Parekh, 2012). On university campuses, hate speech often takes subtle forms such as jokes, stereotypes, derogatory nicknames, and hostile online posts, making it difficult to regulate (Akinola & Adesina, 2020). Hate Speech refers to any form of verbal, written, or symbolic expression that demeans, stereotypes, or incites hostility against individuals or groups based on ethnicity, religion, political affiliation, gender, or other identity markers (Waldron, 2012). Hate speech denotes any speech that disparage an individual or a group based on their race, colour, ethnicity, gender, handicap, sexual orientation, nationality, religion, or other characteristics (Ezinwa, Ngu, odili & Ekwu, 20016 cited in Babatunde, 2023). It also refers to expressions spoken, written, or symbolic that demean, dehumanize, or incite hostility against individuals or groups based on identity markers such as ethnicity, religion, nationality, gender, or political affiliation (Waldron, 2012). From ethnic slurs exchanged in hostels, to religious intolerance during student gatherings, to inflammatory posts on WhatsApp and X (formerly Twitter), campus interactions increasingly mirror the divisions in the wider society. These developments raise critical concerns about campus unity and the moral role of higher education institutions.

While freedom of expression is fundamental in academic settings, hate speech crosses ethical boundaries when it threatens dignity, equality, and peaceful coexistence. On campuses, hate speech may not always appear as overt violence. It often emerges through ethnic stereotyping, derogatory nicknames, online harassment, exclusionary narratives, and the politicization of student associations along identity lines for example *an or* MINDA, Tyosin, Kparev, Fulani, Igbo Yoruba etc. though these associations are targeted to unite the students on campuses, some hate speech like “an or” literally translated as “small person” are demeaning in nature which denotes hate speech in our daily social interactions on campuses. Other examples of hate acts include discrimination against ethnicity, colour and disability, sex and religion which are ongoing on campuses. Studies indicate that social media has intensified the circulation of hate speech among students, allowing anonymity and rapid dissemination of harmful narratives (Uduak & Ibanga, 2021). These expressions often target ethnic and religious identities, reinforcing existing social cleavages.

Hate Speech and Campus Disunity

Campus disunity refers to the breakdown of social cohesion, trust, and collective identity among students. According to Durkheim (1893), social solidarity is sustained by shared norms and values; when these are undermined, social fragmentation occurs. Within the context of the study, Campus Disunity is considered as condition characterized by social fragmentation, mistrust, exclusion, and weakened collective identity among students within a university environment. Empirical studies show that hate speech contributes to intergroup suspicion, avoidance, and hostility among students (Okoye, 2019). Victims of hate speech often withdraw from social interactions, while perpetrators develop hardened in-group identities that promote exclusion (Tajfel & Turner, 1979).

Conceptualizing Positive Values and Social Co-existence

Positive Values

Positive values refer to enduring moral principles and normative standards that guide individual and collective behavior toward socially desirable outcomes. In social science literature, values are understood

as trans-situational goals that serve as guiding principles in people's lives, influencing attitudes, decisions, and social interactions (Schwartz, 1992; Schwartz, 2012). Positive values, in particular, emphasize prosocial orientations such as respect for human dignity, tolerance of diversity, empathy, fairness, and responsibility. Schwartz's Theory of Basic Human Values identifies values such as **benevolence** (concern for the welfare of others) and **universalism** (understanding, tolerance, and protection of all people) as foundational to peaceful and cohesive societies (Schwartz, 2012). These values promote inclusivity and discourage behaviors that marginalize or dehumanize others. Within university environments, positive values function as moral anchors that regulate student conduct, shape peer relations, and foster respectful engagement across ethnic, religious, and ideological differences. From a sociological perspective, positive values are not merely individual attributes but socially constructed norms transmitted through institutions such as families, schools, religious bodies, and peer groups (Durkheim, 1893). Universities play a critical role in value socialization by modeling ethical conduct, encouraging dialogue, and reinforcing norms of mutual respect. Where positive values are weak or inconsistently enforced, social interactions become vulnerable to hostility, stereotyping, and hate speech. In the context of this study, positive values are conceptualized as learned and reinforced moral orientations such as tolerance, respect, empathy, dialogue, and fairness that discourage hate speech and promote inclusive interaction among undergraduate students.

Social Co-existence

Social co-existence refers to the ability of individuals and groups with diverse identities, beliefs, and backgrounds to live and interact peacefully within a shared social space. It involves mutual recognition, acceptance of difference, and the maintenance of social relationships based on respect and cooperation (Galtung, 1996). Social coexistence does not imply the absence of conflict, but rather the capacity to manage differences constructively without resorting to hostility or exclusion. In pluralistic societies, social coexistence is sustained through shared norms, institutional trust, and inclusive social practices (Putnam, 2000). Durkheim (1893) argued that social cohesion depends on moral consensus, which enables individuals to perceive themselves as part of a collective whole. When this consensus is weakened through hate speech, discrimination, or identity-based exclusion social fragmentation and disunity emerge. Within university campuses, social coexistence is reflected in students' willingness to engage across group boundaries, participate in collective activities, and resolve disagreements through dialogue rather than confrontation. Empirical studies show that campuses characterized by strong social coexistence experience lower levels of conflict, higher academic engagement, and improved student wellbeing (Gurin et al., 2013). Positive values and social co-existence are intrinsically interconnected. Positive values provide the moral framework, while social co-existence represents the practical outcome of those values in everyday interactions. In the absence of positive values, social coexistence becomes fragile, especially in contexts marked by diversity and historical grievances.

Empirical studies demonstrate that campuses that emphasize tolerance, respect, and dialogue experience lower levels of intergroup tension and higher levels of student integration (Williams & Tregidga, 2018). Conversely, environments where values education is neglected tend to reproduce broader societal divisions, leading to persistent disunity. In this study, positive values are conceptualized as mediating variables capable of weakening the negative impact of hate speech on campus unity.

Prevalence of Hate Speech among Undergraduate Students

Hate speech among university students has emerged as a significant concern in educational and digital environments globally. Defined as expressions that demean, stereotype, or incite hostility against individuals or groups based on identity markers such as ethnicity, religion, gender, or political affiliation, hate speech is not confined to public politics or online platforms. It permeates campus social life as well (Waldron, 2012). Several studies show that hate speech is pervasive among undergraduates both in face-to-face and digital spaces. For instance, Uduak and Ibanga (2021) found high rates of identity-based derogatory expressions on Nigerian campuses, particularly on social media platforms like WhatsApp and Twitter, where students often share inflammatory content under the guise of humour or political commentary. Similarly, Akinola and Adesina (2020) reported that online forums associated with university student groups tend to amplify ethnic and religious hostility during heated academic and

political events. Some studies reveal that hate speech tends to concentrate around salient identity fault lines common within higher education environments. Ethnic stereotyping and inter-religious taunting were reported as frequent forms of student-generated hate speech in studies conducted across Nigerian universities (Okoye, 2019; Uduak & Ibanga, 2021). Regional and political tropes also serve as vehicles for targeted hostility, especially during student elections and national sociopolitical crises (Adesoji, 2020).

How Hate Speech Contributes to Campus Disunity

Campus disunity is a state of weakened social cohesion, marked by mistrust, exclusion, and intergroup polarization among students. Hate speech operates as a central catalyst for these phenomena. Hate speech amplifies these dynamics by signalling derogatory norms toward out-groups, thereby solidifying divisions. When students engage in ethnic or religious insults, they not only demean others but also communicate entrenched group boundaries that discourage cross-group interaction (Williams & Tregidga, 2018). Empirical studies reveal that hate speech disrupts everyday campus relations. Okoye (2019) reported that ethnic slurs and regional stereotyping create social avoidance patterns among students, leading to cliques and fragmented peer networks. Uduak and Ibanga (2021) found that repeated exposure to hostile online content leads students to self-segregate in physical spaces, such as dining halls and hostels, out of fear or discomfort. Hate speech also undermines trust in institutional culture. Students perceiving their peers as hostile are less likely to participate in collaborative learning, student governance, or intergroup events (Gurin et al., 2013). This erosion of shared norms contributes to a highly fragmented campus climate where collective identity is weakened.

Perceived Consequences of Hate Speech on Social Relations and Student Interactions

Hate speech has multidimensional consequences, affecting students' emotional wellbeing, social relations, academic engagement, and overall campus experience. Exposure to hate speech has been associated with elevated psychological stress, anxiety, and reduced sense of belonging. Williams and Tregidga (2018) observed that students who reported frequent encounters with hate speech were more likely to feel isolated and emotionally distressed. This emotional burden can undermine students' confidence, participation, and campus enjoyment. Studies show that victims or even bystanders of hate speech often engage in social withdrawal as a coping strategy. In their research, Uduak and Ibanga (2021) found that students subjected to or witnessing hate speech were more likely to avoid social spaces where their identities might be targeted, leading to decreased campus sociability and weakened social networks. The repercussions of hate speech also extend into academic domains. Research indicates that hostile peer environments diminish students' willingness to participate in class discussions, group projects, and academic collaborations (Williams & Tregidga, 2018). Reduced interaction across groups limits intellectual exchange and can negatively impact overall learning outcomes. Research indicates that hate speech negatively affects students' psychological well-being, academic engagement, and sense of belonging (Williams & Tregidga, 2018). In Nigerian universities, hate-laden student politics and online discourse have escalated tensions during elections and protests, sometimes resulting in violence (Adesoji, 2020).

Positive Values as Promoters of Social Co-existence and Unity

Positive values such as respect, tolerance, empathy, and dialogue are widely recognized in the literature as key elements for fostering peaceful coexistence in diverse social environments. Allport's (1954) Contact Hypothesis argues that structured interaction between diverse groups can reduce prejudice if grounded in equality and cooperative goals. Follow-up studies applying this framework in educational settings found that intergroup dialogue programmes reduce hostility and increase mutual respect among students (Gurin et al., 2013). Empirical work points to several campus interventions that leverage positive values to strengthen coexistence. Schwartz et al. (2012) reported that universities that integrate ethics curricula, peer mediation initiatives, and mentorship programmes significantly improve student attitudes toward diversity. Such interventions are effective because they shift campus culture from individual competition toward collective respect and cooperation.

Theoretical Framework: Social Solidarity and Social Value Theory

Emile Durkheim first elaborated the concept of social solidarity in *The Division of Labour in Society* (1893) and further expanded the role of shared values and collective conscience in *The Elementary Forms of Religious Life* (1912). Émile Durkheim's theory of social solidarity is anchored on the idea that society is held together by shared norms, values, beliefs, and moral sentiments, which he referred to as the collective conscience. According to Durkheim (1893), social order and cohesion are sustained when individuals internalize common social values that regulate behavior and promote mutual dependence. Durkheim identified two major forms of social solidarity: Mechanical Solidarity, this form of solidarity is characteristic of societies where social cohesion is based on similarity shared beliefs, traditions, and values. Social order is maintained through strong collective norms and moral regulation. Deviations from accepted norms, such as hate speech, are strongly sanctioned because they threaten social cohesion (Durkheim, 1893). Organic Solidarity on the other hand emerges in more complex societies characterized by diversity and specialization. Social cohesion is achieved through interdependence rather than similarity. In such societies, tolerance, respect, and cooperation become essential social values for maintaining unity amid diversity (Durkheim, 1893).

Durkheim further emphasized that social values function as moral facts, external to individuals yet coercive, guiding acceptable behavior within society. When shared values weaken, society experiences anomie, a state of normlessness that leads to social disorder, conflict, and disintegration (Durkheim, 1912). Despite its enduring relevance, Durkheim's theory has attracted several critiques. Critics argue that Durkheim places excessive emphasis on consensus and social cohesion while underestimating the role of power, inequality, and conflict in social life (Cosser, 1956). From a conflict perspective, social norms and values may reflect dominant group interests rather than collective agreement. Additionally, Durkheim's distinction between mechanical and organic solidarity has been criticized for oversimplifying the complexity of modern societies, where multiple forms of solidarity often coexist (Giddens, 1971).

Nevertheless, these critiques do not invalidate the theory's utility especially on critical social problem like hate speech and crimes. First, hate speech represents a violation of collective moral values that sustain social solidarity within the university community. By promoting exclusion and hostility, hate speech weakens the collective conscience and contributes to anomic conditions, characterized by mistrust, fragmentation, and campus disunity (Durkheim, 1893). Second, the diversity of undergraduate populations reflects conditions of organic solidarity, where unity depends on interdependence and respect for difference rather than similarity. In this context, positive values such as tolerance, empathy, and dialogue become essential for sustaining social cohesion. Third, the study's emphasis on promoting positive values aligns with Durkheim's assertion that social institutions especially educational institutions are central to the transmission and reinforcement of moral values. Universities function as moral communities responsible for socializing individuals into shared norms that promote peaceful coexistence (Durkheim, 1912). Thus, the theory explains both the causes of campus disunity (erosion of shared values through hate speech) and the pathways to restoring unity (strengthening collective values and moral regulation).

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a mixed-methods research design, combining quantitative survey methods with qualitative in-depth interviews to ensure triangulation and depth. The study adopted a survey research design. Survey research is useful in answering questions such as who, what, when, where, and how concerning a particular social problem. This study was carried out at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi (MOAUM) which is a public university owned by the Benue State Government. The university's location strategically positions it to serve students from both urban and rural communities across Benue and neighbouring states including Nasarawa, Taraba, and Plateau.

The population of this study comprised all full-time undergraduate students enrolled at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi (MOAUM) during the 2024/2025 academic session. As at the 2024/2025 academic session, the university has 31,451 undergraduates across its fourteen faculties and 61 departments (bsum.edu.ng). This population is appropriate for the study because undergraduate students

at MOAUM indulge in hate speech and hate crimes in their daily interaction. Taro Yamane’s (1967) formula, was used to determine the sample size of 400 students. A multistage sampling technique involving stratified and simple random sampling was employed. Additionally, 15 students were purposively selected for in-depth interviews. Data were collected using: structured questionnaires and semi-structured interview guides. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis, while qualitative data were thematically analyzed. Informed consent, confidentiality, and anonymity were strictly observed.

DATA PRESENTATION AND RESULTS

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Variables

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	220	55.0
	Female	180	45.0
Age (Years)	16–20	140	35.0
	21–25	200	50.0
	26 and above	60	15.0
Academic Level	100 Level	90	22.5
	200 Level	110	27.5
	300 Level	120	30.0
	400 Level	80	20.0
Religion	Christianity	330	82.5
	Islam	55	13.8
	Others	15	3.7
Ethnic Background	Majority ethnic groups	260	65.0
	Minority ethnic groups	140	35.0
Total		400	100.0

The socio-demographic profile of the 400 respondents on table 1 indicates a relatively balanced gender distribution, with 55% male and 45% female students. This suggests that both genders are meaningfully represented, allowing for gender-inclusive insights into experiences of hate speech and campus disunity. In terms of age, the majority of respondents (50%) were between 25 years, followed by 35% aged, and 15% aged 26 years and above. This reflects a 21 and predominantly youthful undergraduate population, which 16–20 years is significant given that students in these age ranges are particularly influenced by peer interactions, social identity dynamics, and exposure to online and offline campus discourses. Regarding academic level, respondents were distributed across all undergraduate years, with 300-level (30%) and 200-level students (27.5%) forming the largest proportions, followed by 100-level (22.5%) and 400-level students (20%). This distribution ensures a comprehensive understanding of students’ perceptions across different stages of university experience, from newcomers to near-graduates.

The religious composition shows a predominance of Christian students (82.5%), followed by Muslims (13.8%) and adherents of other religions (3.7%). This reflects the regional religious demographics of Benue State and highlights the importance of considering minority religious experiences in discussions on campus social cohesion. Finally, the ethnic background indicates that 65% of respondents belong to majority ethnic groups, while 35% are from minority ethnic groups. This diversity underscores the potential for intergroup tensions and reinforces the relevance of the study’s focus on hate speech and

social coexistence. The socio-demographic characteristics reveal a pluralistic and youthful student population, with diversity across gender, age, academic level, religion, and ethnicity. Such diversity presents both opportunities and challenges for campus social cohesion. The prevalence of hate speech and its impact on campus disunity must therefore be understood within this context, emphasizing the need for interventions that promote positive values, tolerance, and inclusive interactions across demographic lines

Table 2: Prevalence of Forms of Hate Speech Among Undergraduate Students

Form of Hate Speech	Percentage (%)
Ethnic Stereotyping	62
Religious Intolerance	48
Political Insults	41
Online Hate Speech	55

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Interpretation:

Table 2 indicates that ethnic stereotyping (62%) is the most prevalent form of hate speech among undergraduate students, followed closely by online hate speech (55%). Religious intolerance (48%) and political insults (41%) also constitute significant forms of hate expression on campus. This confirms that hate speech is multi-dimensional and deeply embedded in both physical and digital student interactions.

Figure 1: Pie Chart Showing Distribution of Hate Speech Forms

Prevalence of Hate Speech Forms Among Undergraduate Students

Interpretation:

Figure 1 visually demonstrates the dominance of ethnic and online hate speech, accounting for over half of reported experiences. The prominence of online hate speech underscores the role of social media in amplifying hostile narratives among students, consistent with findings by Akinola and Adesina (2020).

Table 3: How Hate Speech Influences Campus Disunity

Statement	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Total (%)
Hate speech increases mistrust among students	180 (45%)	140 (35%)	60 (15%)	20 (5%)	100%
Hate speech promotes segregation of students along ethnic/religious lines	160 (40%)	150 (37.5%)	70 (17.5%)	20 (5%)	100%
Hate speech discourages intergroup interactions	150 (37.5%)	160 (40%)	70 (17.5%)	20 (5%)	100%
Hate speech leads to conflicts and disputes on campus	170 (42.5%)	140 (35%)	70 (17.5%)	20 (5%)	100%
Hate speech weakens trust in student leadership and university authorities	130 (32.5%)	150 (37.5%)	90 (22.5%)	30 (7.5%)	100%

Interpretation

The table reveals that a majority of students perceive hate speech as a significant driver of campus disunity: Mistrust Among Students: 80% of respondents (SA + A) agree that hate speech fosters mistrust, highlighting its role in eroding peer relationships. Segregation along Identity Lines: 77.5% agree that hate speech encourages students to self-segregate by ethnicity or religion, confirming Social Identity Theory predictions (Tajfel & Turner, 1979). Reduced Intergroup Interaction: 77.5% report that hate speech discourages cross-group interactions, which can weaken collaboration and informal peer networks. Conflicts and Disputes: 77.5% agree that hate speech contributes to conflicts, including verbal and minor physical disputes, reinforcing campus fragmentation. Erosion of Trust in Leadership: 70% believe that hate speech undermines confidence in student leaders and university authorities, indicating the institutional ramifications of social disunity. The findings empirically demonstrate that hate speech is not merely a social nuisance but a structural threat to campus cohesion. It negatively affects trust, peer relationships, intergroup cooperation, and institutional authority. Interventions must therefore focus on value-based education, mediation, and institutional policies to mitigate the divisive effects of hate speech on student life.

Table 4: Social and Academic Implications of Hate Speech on Student Coexistence

Implication Statement	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Total (%)
Hate speech causes social withdrawal from peers	140 (35%)	130 (32.5%)	90 (22.5%)	40 (10%)	100%
Hate speech negatively affects collaborative learning and group projects	120 (30%)	140 (35%)	100 (25%)	40 (10%)	100%
Hate speech reduces students' participation in campus activities	130 (32.5%)	150 (37.5%)	90 (22.5%)	30 (7.5%)	100%
Hate speech increases psychological stress and anxiety	150 (37.5%)	140 (35%)	80 (20%)	30 (7.5%)	100%
Hate speech diminishes trust and cooperation among students	160 (40%)	130 (32.5%)	80 (20%)	30 (7.5%)	100%

Source: **Field Survey, 2026**

Interpretation

The table 4 indicates that hate speech has both social and academic consequences that undermine student coexistence: Social Withdrawal 67.5% of respondents (SA + A) reported withdrawing from peer interactions due to exposure to hate speech. This withdrawal limits opportunities for positive social

engagement and peer support. Impact on Collaborative Learning, 65% of respondents indicated that hate speech negatively affects participation in group projects and academic collaboration, suggesting that intergroup tension spills over into academic spaces. Reduced Campus Participation, 70% reported avoiding campus activities or events where diversity may expose them to hostility, indicating a decline in overall student engagement and community participation. Psychological Stress, 72.5% agreed that hate speech increases stress and anxiety, highlighting the emotional toll of identity-based hostility and its potential impact on mental wellbeing. Erosion of Trust and Cooperation, 72.5% noted that hate speech diminishes trust and cooperative behaviors among students, reinforcing Social Solidarity Theory's assertion that weakened shared values lead to social fragmentation (Durkheim, 1893). Hate speech does not only affect social relationships but also compromises academic collaboration, participation, and **mental** wellbeing, which are critical for a cohesive university environment. The findings underscore the need for interventions that combine moral education, peer mentorship, and institutional policies to safeguard both social and academic dimensions of student coexistence.

Table 5: Role of Positive Values in Promoting Unity Among Students

Statement	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Total (%)
Tolerance among students promotes peaceful coexistence	150 (37.5%)	140 (35%)	70 (17.5%)	40 (10%)	100%
Respect for diversity enhances intergroup cooperation	160 (40%)	130 (32.5%)	70 (17.5%)	40 (10%)	100%
Empathy and understanding reduce conflicts on campus	140 (35%)	150 (37.5%)	80 (20%)	30 (7.5%)	100%
Dialogue and open communication foster unity among students	130 (32.5%)	160 (40%)	70 (17.5%)	40 (10%)	100%
Mentorship and value-based orientation promote mutual respect	140 (35%)	150 (37.5%)	80 (20%)	30 (7.5%)	100%

Source: **Field Survey, 2026**

Interpretation

The table highlights that positive values are central to fostering unity and social coexistence among undergraduate students: Tolerance, 72.5% of respondents (SA + A) agreed that tolerance reduces hostility and promotes peaceful interactions. Tolerance allows students to navigate differences in ethnicity, religion, or opinion without conflict. Respect for Diversity, 72.5% reported that respect for diverse perspectives and backgrounds enhances intergroup cooperation. This aligns with Durkheim's (1893) Social Solidarity Theory, which posits that shared moral values maintain social cohesion. Empathy and Understanding, 72.5% agreed that empathy minimizes conflict, encouraging students to consider others' feelings and experiences before acting, thereby strengthening peer relationships. Dialogue and Open Communication, 72.5% emphasized that open, respectful dialogue allows students to address disagreements constructively, preventing miscommunication from escalating into conflict. Mentorship and Value-based Orientation, 72.5% indicated that structured mentorship programmes and orientation sessions reinforce moral and social values, cultivating a culture of mutual respect and unity on campus. The findings demonstrate that embedding positive values into campus culture is a practical and effective strategy to mitigate hate speech and enhance social cohesion. University administrators should implement value-based education, mentorship programs, and intergroup dialogue platforms to cultivate tolerance, respect, and empathy among students, thereby promoting unity and sustainable coexistence.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings demonstrate that hate speech plays a critical role in undermining campus unity at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University. The dominance of ethnic stereotyping confirms the continued salience of identity politics among Nigerian youths, supporting Social Identity Theory’s assertion that individuals often assert in-group superiority through out-group derogation (Tajfel & Turner, 1979). The strong statistical relationship between hate speech and campus disunity reinforces Durkheim’s (1893) argument that social cohesion depends on shared norms and values. Where hate speech flourishes, these norms are weakened, resulting in mistrust, exclusion, and social fragmentation. Furthermore, students’ recognition of respect, tolerance, and empathy as solutions supports Schwartz’s Values Theory, which emphasizes universal moral values as foundations for peaceful coexistence (Schwartz, 2012)

Table 6: Regression Analysis Showing the Effect of Hate Speech on Campus Disunity

Variable	Beta Coefficient	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Hate Speech Exposure	0.63	0.08	7.88	0.000

Dependent Variable: Campus Disunity

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Interpretation of Regression Results

The regression result reveals a positive and statistically significant relationship between hate speech exposure and campus disunity ($\beta = 0.63, p < 0.05$). This indicates that increased exposure to hate speech significantly predicts higher levels of disunity among undergraduate students. The strong beta coefficient suggests that hate speech is a major explanatory factor in campus fragmentation, validating the study’s central assumption and aligning with earlier empirical findings (Waldron, 2012; Okoye, 2019).

Integrated Discussion

Taken together, the analyses reveal a clear empirical chain: Hate speech → campus disunity → social and academic disruption. Positive values → improved coexistence → restored unity. This confirms that while hate speech fractures campus life, value-based education and mentorship offer sustainable solutions. Universities that fail to address value deficits risk reproducing societal conflicts within academic spaces.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that hate speech significantly contributes to campus disunity among undergraduates, both socially and academically, by promoting mistrust, segregation, conflict, and social withdrawal. These outcomes corroborate Durkheim’s (1893) Social Solidarity Theory, which posits that weakened shared values lead to social fragmentation and anomie.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study recommends the following:

1. The university should incorporate courses and workshops on ethics, tolerance, conflict resolution, and social responsibility into the undergraduate curriculum to cultivate positive values and mitigate hate speech.
2. The University should establish mentorship and peer guidance initiatives where senior students model positive behaviors and provide support to juniors, fostering an environment of empathy, respect, and dialogue.
3. The state Government and University should implement strict institutional policies against hate speech, including clear definitions, reporting mechanisms, and sanctions for violations, to deter acts of verbal aggression and promote accountability.
4. Intensive awareness campaigns should be conducted by stakeholders in the education through seminars, posters, and social media to educate students on the harmful effects of hate speech and the benefits of positive values for social cohesion.

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